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Research Article

Comparative Study of Panchamrut Herbal Face Scrub and Everyuth Walnut Face Scrub

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ABSTRACT

The process of blending natural ingredients in specific ratios to create a product is called formulation. In the case of a facial scrub, the ingredients are selected based on their properties to exfoliate, moisturize, and nourish the skin. The formulation process aims to achieve a balance of efficacy and gentleness. To remain healthy and to appear good, the skin surface requires periodic cleansing to remove dirt, sebum and other secretions, dead cells, crusts, applied make-ups, atmospheric change, and irregular life style. Use of chemical based topical applications extends fast deterioration of skin and their appendix. This requires immediate and suitable procedure which can not only extend benefits to the skin but also helpful in long duration making your skin look charming. In this scrub milk, curd, sugar, honey, ghee, orange peel powder, rice flour, clove oil, rosehip oil, sandalwood powder. The scrub was evaluated by using the parameters such as deep cleansing of pores, smoothening effect, skin glow and effect on pimple. This is a clinical study to evaluate transdermal safety and efficacy of the herbal formulation. The use of natural ingredients to fight against acne, wrinkle and also to control secretion of oil and to remove tan.

INTRODUCTION

A beauty product or remedy which cleanses and exfoliates the pores and skin of the face. A weekly facial scrub is vital for a wholesome complexion. The growing demand for natural and herbal skincare products has led to significant interest in formulating cosmetics with safe, effective, and

eco-friendly ingredients. Among these, facial scrubs play a vital role in exfoliating the skin, removing dead cells, and promoting a healthy, radiant complexion. This project focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a facial scrub that incorporates Panchamrut, an ancient Ayurvedic blend of five natural ingredients, known for

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nourishing and skin-enhancing properties. Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purposes of cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness relating to treatment intended to restore or improve the persons alternating to the good appearance. From the ancient time, different herbs are used for cleaning, beautifying and to manage them. The first and major advantage of the use of a facial scrub is disposing of the useless pores and skin cells out of your face. Dead pores and skin cells make your face appearance dry and dull. These additionally clog your pores and skin pores. Facial scrubs exfoliate your pores and skin very well and cast off the useless pores and skin cells. Human beings have been using herbs for different purposes like food, medicine, and beautifying. With the advancement of science and technology, use of natural things including plants has been reduced except for food. Since herbal cosmetics is not mentioned under schedule S to the drugs and cosmetics rules, both types and preparations i.e. all herbal and the once that have the cosmetic base to which has been added one or more herbal ingredients, are available in the market. Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purposes of cleansing, beautifying, and promoting attractiveness relating to treatment intended to restore or improve the person's alternating to a good appearance. From ancient time, different herbs are used for cleaning, beautifying and managing them. Face skin is the major part of the body, which indicates the health of an individual, Cosmetics are available as various forms and each has its own role to play on the skin. Skin becomes dull, and non-glowing due to various causes and these can effectively be overcome with the application of scrubs. There are two types of scrub being used on the skin such as facial scrub and body scrub. These two differ only with the ratios of oil and sugar added in each. It removes the dead skin cell and exfoliates the skin. Scrub can be used on any type of skin.

Advantages Of Herbal Facial Scrub:

- Provides Smoother Skin. Apart from the above, face scrubs also make your skin surface smooth and glowing.
- Scrubbing your skin improves blood circulation, boosts cell turnover, and reduces the appearance of blemishes.
- Removes Dead Skin Cells.
- The first and foremost benefit of using a facial scrub is removing the dead skin cells from your face.
- A facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product used to exfoliate and clean the skin on the face and body.
- Facial skin is sensitive, thinner, and more prone to damage as compared to the skin on other parts of the body.
- Skin on the face is in regular contact with dirt, pollution, and other contaminants.
- The physical act of scrubbing can improve blood flow, which can brighten the skin.

2. Review Of Literature

Shruti Satish Garad, Chinni Tejas Gajanan, Choudhari Mohammad Sami Mohammad Toufhik, Rohit Shahaji Bhosale and Abhishek Chavan et al (2024) The primary aim of the current investigation was to develop a polyherbal exfoliant integrated into a gel matrix. Utilization of botanical components for combating acne, wrinkles, and regulating sebum production is referred to as natural or herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmeceuticals typically feature botanical extracts with antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-aging attributes. Herbal cosmetics are considered the most benign option for regular application due to their lack of adverse reactions, whereas cosmeceuticals are formulations that modulate the physiological functions of the skin. Polly Gupta, Shashank Tiwari, Kartikay Prakash, Trivid Shukla, Preeti Yadav et al (2024) In today's life for both

women and men cosmetics plays an important role to beautifying and altering the appearance of skin. The use of natural ingredients to remain healthy and of good appearance, the skin surface requires frequent cleansing to remove oil, sebum and other secretions, dead cells, crusts and applied make-ups. Aim: This study aims on the formulating an herbal Face Scrub using natural ingredients incorporated into gel, For the purpose of enhancing skin beauty, several skin conditions are developed, such as skin protection, sunscreen, anti-acne, and anti-wrinkle products. Siddhi Pise , Fareed Shaikh, Payaam Vohra et al (2023) During the puberty, an imbalance of internal constituents and hormonal balance may cause many skin problems. Acne is found as a most common skin problem. The current proposal aims to unfold the potential benefits of coriander to combat acne problems. Medicinal plants are used all over the world to treat various diseases due to its variety of phytochemical constituents. Ideally, topical therapy is the primary treatment for many skin diseases. Among the various topical formulations, face scrub has been considered as a potential vehicle due to its non-sticky nature, stability and greater aesthetic value. The objective of this proposed study was to develop a herbal topical facial scrub formulation containing *Coriandrum sativum* to treat acne and serve as a safe, effective and alternative therapy to the current conventional harmful antibiotics. Harshal Kishor Patil, Bhavinee Paramanand Patil, Narendra Sadu Patil, Vaibhav Vinod Patel, Truptesh Rajendra Pardeshi et al (2023) The major goal of the research project was to create herbal scrub employing organic materials mixed into gel. Cosmetics have a significant part in today's society for both men and women in beautifying and changing the appearance of skin. The skin surface needs frequent washing to remove oil, sebum, and other secretions, dead cells, crusts, and applied make-ups in order to maintain its health and beauty. The

usage of herbal cosmetics is growing since they have little or no adverse effect. Ms. Dethe Akanksha Ashok, Ms. Dhokale Manasvi Avinash, Mrs. Shelke Dipali S et al (2023) Scrub is the agent which is used to remove the dead cell from skin , pigmentation and blackheads, white heads and make skin glowing, smooth, soft and healthy. Scrub can be directly applied onto the skin by gently massage is recommended on application of the scrub which helps to improve blood circulation and increase oxygen supply to all surface of the skin. In today's human life face scrubs are quite popular and achieved more amount of success in low cost. Fariah Rizwani, Khush Jain and Dr. Shefali Thakkar et al (2023) Natural remedies are much more acceptable than any synthetic formulations in today's genre. Herbal formulations have a growing demand in the world market. These days' western countries have increased their dependency on natural herbal products which has witnessed in lightning advancement in Indian Herbal market for our herbal formulations. The plants have been reported in literature having good anti-microbial activity, anti-oxidant activity and anti-inflammatory activities. Shoeb Akhtar, Shivani Saini, Dr. S.M. Patil et al (2023) To formulate and evaluate facial herbal scrub by using sesame seeds. The scrub was prepared by using the that is sesame seeds powder, rice powder, orange peel powder, turmeric, tulsi powder, water, vitamin E oil, glycerin. The scrub was prepared by homogenous mixing of all the excipients together. Nikhil N. Jadhav, Chaitali Ghumre, Chaitali Garadand Parmeshwar Ghongate et al (2023) To remain healthy and to appear good, the skin surface requires periodic cleansing to remove dirt, sebum and other secretions, deadcells, crusts, applied make-ups, atmospheric change, and irregular life style. Use of chemical based topical applications extends fast deterioration of skin and their appendix. This requires immediate and suitable procedure which can not only extend

benefits to the skin but also helpful in long duration making your skin look charming. Cosmetics play a vital role for everyone to have a joyful and sanguine life. In present scenario herbal Cosmeceuticals have more demand because they have no side effects. People having oily skin suffer from acne, whiteheads and blackheads quite often so scrubbing become more essential. To remain healthy and of good appearance, the skinsurface requires frequent cleansing to remove grin, sebus and other secretions, dead cells, crusts and applied make-ups. The current present work is based upon the compounding of the herbal facial scrub by using an identical combination of the herbal drugs. Ms. Varsha S. Marathe, Ms. Akanksha P. Nikum, Mr. Gautam S. Marathe, Ms. Sulbha G. Patil, Mrs. Sunila A. Patil. et al (2023) Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purpose of beautifying, cleansing, promoting attractiveness or alternating the appearance. The aim of study is to formulate and evaluate a face scrub with incorporation of the sapodilla as an active ingredient. For the purpose of enhancing skin beauty, several skin conditions are developed, such as skin protection, sunscreen, anti-acne, and anti-wrinkle products. Despite the enormous health benefits of synthetic substances, which once more cause environmental destruction, demand for herbal items and cosmetics is rising daily. Due to their dual functionality as medications and cosmetics, herbal cosmetics are in high demand nowadays. The name itself indicates that herbal cosmetics are natural and they do not contain any chemicals. Natural ingredients have no side effects, making them the safest and greatest products to use on a daily basis. A facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product used to exfoliate and clean the skin of the face and body. Blackheads, whiteheads, sebum, and skin cells can all be removed by using face scrubs. Jadhav Akshay Laxman et al (2023) The main objective of present study was to prepare a herbal scrub incorporated into gel. The use of natural

ingredients to fight against acne, wrinkle and also to control secretion of oil is known as natural or herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmetically usually contain the plant parts which possess antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-aging properties. Herbal cosmetics are the safest product to use routine with no side effects and cosmeceuticals are the product which influences the biological function of skin. Rutuja Prashan Nangare, Trupti Ashok Thangeet al (2022) The main objective of present was to prepare a polyherbal scrub incorporated into gel. The use of natural ingredients to fight against acne, wrinkle and also tocontrol secretion of oil is known as natural or herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmeceuticals usually contain the plant parts which possess antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti- aging properties. Herbal cosmetics are the safest product to use routine with no side effects and cosmeceuticals are the product which influences thebiological function of skin. as natural or herbal cosmetics. Vidya Keshav Kakad, Nishigandha Nandkishor Dhokale,Rutuja Sanjay Sanap, Shahina Rafique Sayyed et al (2022) Many of the marketed products when applied on the skin cause dryness of skin after its long-term use which results less life of skin problems of acne and redness. Solution for this problem is use of scrub which consist all herbal ingredients which increases cleansing, softening, moisturizing, fairness of skin. The use of natural ingredients to fight against acne, wrinkle and also to control secretion of oil is known as natural or herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmeceuticals usually contain the plant parts which possess antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti- aging properties. Herbal cosmetics are the safest product to use routine with no side effects and cosmeceuticals are the product which influences the biological function of skin. Dr. Shweta P. Ghode, Vibhavari M. Chatur,Dr. Prashant D. Ghode, Nikhil Shaha, Satyajeeet Prajapati and Atul Thorave et al (2019) The main

objective of the present study was to prepare polyherbal scrub. Nowadays cosmetic have become an important part in the day to day life for both men & women to lead a happy & confident life. Keeping in the mind that the cosmetic should be free from synthetic chemicals/Drug, so we came on conclusion to prepare & evaluate a polyherbal facial scrub to prevent Acne, Scars, Tanning, Wrinkles, Aging, and Redness. This facial scrub content herb which shows Antioxidants, Antiseptic, Antibacterial, Skin brightener, Diminish permanent marks & Reducing inflammation properties. Manorama S. Pardeshi, Ashwini S. Pundkar, Prachi M. Murkute, Syeda Saher Naaz, Pratik Joshi et al (2022) To remain healthy and to appear good, the pores and pores and skin ground require periodic cleansing to cast off dirt, sebum and exceptional secretions, dead cells, crusts, carried out make-ups, atmospheric change, and strange life style. The scrub modified into evaluated through using the parameters along with deep cleansing of pores, smoothening effect, pores and pores and skin glow and effect on pimple. Herbal cosmetics usually include the plant additives which personal antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-tan, anti-growing older properties. Pooja Dave, Gira Patel, Devanshi Patel, Binkal Patel, Dipti Patel, G S Chakraborty, Rupal Jani et al (2022) The research aimed to produce an herbal facial scrub. The majority of times, the skin on the face is in regular contact with dirt, pollution, and other contaminants. The scrub comprises various natural components that are safe to use, have fewer adverse effects, and have antibacterial, anti-infective, antioxidant, anti-aging, and moisturizing characteristics. Coffee contains a lot of antioxidant properties. In addition, coffee grounds have a different aroma and a coarse grain and can be used to remove dirt skin cells that have died Yash Agarwal, Sakshi Sharma, Prajwal, Avantika Sharma and Munendra Mohan Varshney et al

(2021) The main objective of the current study is to prepare polyherbal facial scrub. These days' cosmetics have become a significant part of day-to-day life for both men & women to lead a cheerful & confident life. Keeping in mind that Herbs and spices have been used in maintaining and enhancing human beauty because herbs have many beneficial properties, such as sunscreen, anti-aging, moisturizing, antioxidant, anticellulite, and antimicrobial effects. As compared with synthetic cosmetic products, herbal products are mild, biodegradable, and have a low toxicity profile,[3] so we concluded to prepare & evaluate a polyherbal facial scrub to protect Acne, Scars, Tanning, Wrinkles, Aging, and Redness. This facial scrub contains herb which shows Antioxidants, Antiseptic, Antibacterial, Skin brightener, Diminish permanent marks & reducing inflammation properties. Vibhavari M. Chatur, Pooja G. Chaudhari, Jagdish S. Deshmane, Shweta P. Ghode et al (2020) To remain healthy and to appear good, the skin surface requires periodic cleansing to remove dirt, sebum and other secretions, dead cells, crusts, applied make-ups, atmospheric change, and irregular life style. Use of chemical based topical applications extends fast deterioration of skin and their appendix. This requires immediate and suitable procedure which can not only extend benefits to the skin but also helpful in long duration making your skin look charming. Dr. Shweta P. Ghode, Vibhavari M. Chatur, Dr. Prashant D. Ghode, Nikhil Shaha, Satyajeet Prajapati and Atul Thorave et al (2019) The main objective of the present study was to prepare polyherbal scrub. Nowadays cosmetic have become an important part in the day to day life for both men & women to lead a happy & confident life. Keeping in the mind that the cosmetic should be free from synthetic chemicals/Drug, so we came on conclusion to prepare & evaluate a polyherbal facial scrub to prevent Acne, Scars, Tanning, Wrinkles, Aging,

and Redness. This facial scrub content herb which shows Antioxidants, Antiseptic, Antibacterial, Skin brightener, Diminish permanent marks & Reducing inflammation properties. Vidya Keshav Kakad, Nishigandha Nandkishor Dhokale, Rutuja Sanjay Sanap, Shahina Rafique Sayyed et al (2022) Many of the marketed products when applied on the skin cause dryness of skin after its long-term use which results less life of skin problems of acne and redness. Solution for this problem is use of scrub which consist all herbal ingredients which increases cleansing, softening, moisturizing, fairness of skin. The use of natural ingredients to fight against acne, wrinkle and also to control secretion of oil is known as natural or herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmeceuticals usually contain the plant parts which possess antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-aging properties. Herbal cosmetics are the safest product to use routine with no side effects and cosmeceuticals are the product which influences the biological function of skin.

Rational Of the Study: -

Need Of Work: -

□

In current scenario to remain healthy and to appear good, the skin surface requires periodic cleansing to remove dirt, sebum and other secretions, dead cells, crusts, applied make-ups, atmospheric change, and irregular life style. Use of chemical based topical applications extends fast deterioration of skin and their appendix. The scrub was evaluated by using the parameters such as deep cleansing of pores, soothing effect, skin glow and effect on pimple. In the case of a facial scrub, the ingredients are selected based on their properties to exfoliate, moisturize, and nourish the skin.

A. Safety and Gentleness:

- Conventional facial scrubs often contain harsh chemicals, artificial fragrances, and microplastics that can irritate the skin and cause allergic reactions, especially for individuals with sensitive skin.
- Herbal scrubs utilize natural ingredients like oats, honey, yogurt, and herbs, making them gentle and safer for most skin types.

B. Effectiveness:

- Herbal ingredients possess inherent properties that are beneficial for the skin.
- For example, oatmeal soothes inflammation and moisturizes, honey has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties, and yogurt contains lactic acid that promotes exfoliation and cell renewal.

C. Multifaceted Benefits:

- Conventional scrubs often contain microplastics that pose a threat to the environment and marine life.
- Herbal scrubs are often formulated with biodegradable ingredients and sustainable packaging, making them more eco-friendly choice.

D. Affordability:

Compared to expensive commercial scrubs, herbal scrubs can be made at home using readily available ingredients, making them a more affordable option.

Objectives: -

1. To provide a cultural and traditional significance.
2. To give a holistic approach to skin care.
3. To give environmentally sustainable product.

4. To give free from harsh chemical product.
5. To study the preparation of herbal face scrub.
6. To study the preparation of panchamrut herbal face scrub.

3. Plan Of Work: -

- Selection of pure drug
- Identification tests of drug:
 - i. Ferric Chloride Test
 - ii. Aluminium Chloride Test
 - iii. Vinegar Test
 - iv. Aniline Chloride Test
 - v. Fiehe's Test
 - vi. pH Measurement Test
 - vii. Thin Layer Chromatography
 - viii. Folin Ciocalteu method
 - ix. Iodine Test for Starch
- Preparation of reagents
- Experimental design
- Result & discussion
- Conclusion
- Reference

4. Drug Profile: -

1. Milk

Figure no. 5.1 Milk

Synonyms: Dudh

Properties: Moisturizing, Cleansing, Dirt remover

Description:

- **Colour** – Brown
- **Odour** – Aromatic
- **Taste** – Unpleasant

Uses :

- The lactic acid in milk helps retain moisture, leaving your skin soft and hydrated.
- Milk is packed with essential nutrients, including proteins, fats, and vitamins. These components act as natural moisturizers for your skin.
- Regular use of milk on your face can help fade dark spots and promote an even skin tone.
- If you have irritated or inflamed skin due to conditions like eczema or psoriasis, milk can offer relief.
- Its anti-inflammatory properties can calm redness and itching, providing much-needed comfort.
- It removes dead skin cells and impurities, revealing a brighter and more youthful complexion.

2. Curd

Figure no. 5.2 Curd

Synonyms: Dahi

Properties: Exfoliator, Antibacterial, skin hydration, nourishment

Description:

- **Colour-** White
- **Odour** – Milk Odour
- **Taste** – Sour

Uses :

- **Exfoliation:** Curd contains lactic acid, which is an alpha-hydroxy acid (AHA) that exfoliates dead skin cells.
- **Hydration:** Curd's lactic acid helps hydrate skin and fight dryness and cracks.
- **Acne treatment:** Curd's antibacterial and antifungal properties can help fight acne. Curd also contains zinc, which can help reduce inflammation.
- **Skin lightening:** Curd can help lighten skin tone and reverse the effects of tanning.
- **Skin soothing:** Curd can soothe red and irritated skin.
- **Skin tightening:** Curd's lactic acid can help clear clogged pores and prevent breakouts.
- **Skin rejuvenation:** Curd's nutrients and vitamins can help keep skin healthy and beautiful.
- **Skin brightening:** Curd's vitamin B5 can help fade dark spots and give skin a natural glow.

3. Sugar

Figure no. 5.3 Sugar

Synonyms: Sucrose

Molecular formula: C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁

Molecular weight: 342.2965 g/mol

Properties: Exfoliator, Moisturizer, Anti-inflammatory, Cell regeneration

Description:

- **Colour** – White
- **Odour** – Sour
- **Taste** – Sweet

Uses:

- Sugar is a natural humectant meaning it draws moisture from its surroundings into the skin and helps to retain any moisture the skin absorbs.
- Products which contain sugar and its derivatives actually hydrate the complexion and help to keep moisture in the skin leaving it a smooth and plump.
- Suitable for all skin types, sugar wax is an excellent alternative to conventional wax used for hair removal.
- Sugar can help break scar tissues and draw out impurities from pores.

Physicochemical properties-

- **Melting point:** 366°F (186°C).
- **Solubility:** 2000 gm per litre

4. Honey

Figure no 5.4 Honey

Synonyms: Shahad, Madhu, nectar
Molecular formula: C₆H₁₂O₆ **Molecular weight:** 202 g/mol.

Properties: Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Antibacterial

Description:

- **Colour** – Yellowish brown
- **Odour** – Sweet
- **Taste** - Sweet

Uses:

- They also help to treat the redness and inflammation associated with breakouts.
- Honey can also help treat sunburns by reducing inflammation and nourishing damaged tissues.
- Honey is a natural humectant that can deeply hydrate the skin.
- It can also help reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles.
- Honey can help remove dirt and debris that can clog pores.
- Honey can help lighten scars and hyperpigmentation.

Physicochemical properties-

- **Melting point :** 41 °C
- **Solubility:** Soluble in warm water

Ghee

Figure no. 5.5 Ghee

Synonyms: Ghritam, vanaspati ghee
Molecular formula: (C₁₇H₃₃ Co_o)₃ C₃H₅. **Molecular weight:** 255 g/mol

Properties: Anti-Inflammatory, Moisturizer, Anti-Aging, Natural Glow

Description:

- **Colour-** Yellowish or Golden
- **Odour-** Sour
- **Taste-** Sweet

Uses:

- Ghee is a rich source of vitamins.
- Ghee's antioxidants can help prevent and reduce damage from oxidative stress.
- Vitamins A, D, and E and antioxidants help to maintain your skin's elasticity.
- It can also help activate collagen production, which can keep wrinkles at bay.
- Ghee can help heal burns and soothe irritated skin.

- Ghee can be used both internally and externally.
- Externally, ghee soothes and moisturizes, promoting soft, supple skin.

Physicochemical properties-

- **Melting point** : 29°C
- **Solubility:** Insoluble in water

Orange Peel Powder

Figure no 5.6 Orange Peel Powder

Synonyms: Orange Rind

Properties: Anti-Aging, Anti-Inflammatory, Exfoliator
Uses :

- An orange peel skin toner can help tighten pores, control excess oil production and provide a refreshing sensation.
- Orange peel powder can help even out skin tone and brighten it.
- Orange peel powder's gentle abrasive texture removes dead skin cells.
- Orange peel powder's vitamin C content helps keep skin hydrated and moisturized.
- Orange peel powder can absorb excess oil from oily skin.
- Orange peel powder can deep cleanse pores and help with blackheads, whiteheads, acne, and pimples.

Sandalwood Powder

Figure no. 5.7 Sandalwood Powder

Synonyms: Chandan, White sandalwood

Properties: Antiseptic, Reduce redness, Exfoliating, Anti-inflammatory.

Uses:

- Sandalwood has antiseptic properties that can help prevent acne, pimples, and sores.
- Sandalwood powder can help treat dry skin and improve skin cells.
- Sandalwood powder can help reduce hyperpigmentation and dark spots.
- Sandalwood powder can help reduce uneven skin.
- Sandalwood contains natural skin lightening agents and hence is used in many fairness face packs.

Clove Oil

Figure no. 5.8 Clove Oil

Synonyms: Lavang

Molecular formula: C₁₀H₁₂O₂

Molecular weight: 165 g/mol

Properties: Antimicrobial, Antioxidant, Pain-relieving.

Description:

- **Colour** – Dark Brown
- **Odour** – Spicy, Aromatic
- **Taste** – Pungent Warm Spice

Uses:

- Clove oil contains a compound called as eugenol that helps in treating acne.
- Clove oil can help reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles, and prevent sagging skin.
- Clove oil can soothe itching and burning caused by exposure to poison ivy or poison oak. It can also be used to prevent bad scars from forming on skin sores.

Physicochemical properties-

- **Melting point:** 251 °C

- **Solubility:** Slightly soluble in water

Rosehip Oil

Figure no. 5.9 Rosehip Oil

Synonyms : Hip Berry, Dog Rose

Molecular formula:

Monogalactosyldiacylglycerol

Molecular weight: 1.25gram

Properties: Antibacterial, Protects sun damage, Boost immunity, Anti- inflammatory

Uses:

- Rosehip oil is lightweight and easily absorbed by the skin
- Rosehip oil can help improve inflammatory acne and clear up acne scars.
- It contains linoleic acid, a fatty acid that can help prevent acne and shrink pimples.
- Rosehip oil can help fade pigmentation, including dark patches and age or sun spots.
- Rosehip oil can help protect against sun damage.

Physicochemical properties-

- **Melting point** : 10°C

- **Solubility:** Soluble in Oil and Cosmetic ester, but it is insoluble in water and alcohol
- **Melting point:** 221°C
- **Solubility:** Insoluble

10. Rice Flour

Figure no.5.10 Rice Flour

Synonyms: Kernel, Grist, Rice Atta Molecular formula: $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$ Molecular weight : 135g

Properties: Reduce inflammation, Exfoliation, improves skin texture, Brightens skin

Uses:

- Rice flour possesses soothing properties that can help alleviate skin irritation and inflammation.
- Rice flour is a gentle exfoliant that removes dead skin cells and unclogs pores.
- Rice flour can help remove excess oil from the skin, which can be beneficial for oily or acne-prone skin.
- Rice flour can help calm irritated skin and reduce redness.
- Rice flour can help retain moisture in the skin, keeping it hydrated and supple.
- Rice flour can help maintain and repair the skin's natural barrier.

Physicochemical Properties-

Table 6.1: List of materials

Sr. No.	Particular	Quantity
1.	Milk	5 %
2.	Curd	5 %
3.	Sugar	8 %
4.	Honey	5 %
5.	Ghee	5 %
6.	Orange Peel Powder	3 %
7.	Sandalwood Powder	2 %
8.	Clove Oil	2 %
9.	Rosehip Oil	2 %
10.	Rice Flour	10

• Drugs and chemicals:

Milk, curd, Sugar, Honey, Ghee, Orange Peel Powder, Sandalwood Powder, Clove oil, Rosehip Oil, Rice Flour.

• Glassware's and instruments:

Beaker's, Stirrer, Measuring Cylinder, Weighing Balance, Mortar And Pestle, Sieve, Tray dryer.

6.1 Authentication tests of drug

1. Orange Peel Powder:

• Ferric Chloride Test

Add 3–4 drops of 0.1% ferric chloride to a filtered extract of orange peel in a test tube. blue-black or brownish green color indicates the presence of terpenoids.

• Aluminium Chloride Test

Add a few drops of 1% aluminium solution to a portion of the filtrate. A yellow color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

• Phenol-Sulphuric Method

Briefly, 1 mL of aqueous extract, 3 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid, and 0.8 mL of 5% phenol in water were mixed. The tubes containing the mixtures were incubated at 90 °C for 5 min.

2. Honey:

• The Vinegar Test:

Another simple chemical test for the identification of honey involves vinegar. In this test, you need to mix 2 – 3 teaspoons of vinegar in one tablespoon of honey along with some water. The formation of mixture indicates adulteration, which isn't the case if no mixture gets formed.

• Aniline Chloride Test:

This test can detect starch adulterants in honey. The solution turns yellow when starch is present.

• Fiehe's Test:

This test detects artificial invert sugar in honey. The solution turns red when resorcinol and hydrochloric acid are added to the honey.

• Ph Measurement:

Honey is usually mildly acidic, with a pH of around 3.9. A pH below 3.24 indicates improper storage or an impure sample.

3. Clove Oil:

• Thin layer chromatography (TLC):

This is an analytical tool that can be used to identify eugenol and other chemical components in clove extracts.

4. Rosehip Oil:

• Folin-Ciocalteu method:

This method measures the total phenolic compounds (TPC) in rosehip oil. The TPC is expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAEs) per gram of the seed. (The modification consisted of the addition of lithium sulfate and bromine to the phosphotungstic-phosphomolybdic reagent.)

6.2 Method of Preparation:

- All herbal ingredient were dried and grounded using domestic mixer.
- The required quantity of ingredients was weighed and taken.
- Required amount of curd taken in a beaker.
- Add milk, honey, sugar and ghee separately in to it with non-stop and homogeneous stirring.
- Required amount of Clove oil and Rosehip oil taken in separator beaker then add orange peel powder.
- Powder and Sandalwood Powder and mixed.
- Add the contents of steps 01 into step 02 with gentle continuous stirring in a mortar pestle.
- Add Rice Flour and dough was formed.
- The prepared dough was sieved through mesh no.44.
- By this method the dry granules were prepared and dried under the sunlight.
- After drying it was triturated and smooth granules was prepared.
- Lastly stored in a container.

6.3 Marketed Product for Comparative Study:

The Everyuth Walnut Scrub is generally well regarded for exfoliating properties. It effectively removes dead skin cells, promoting smoother and clearer skin.

Formulation:

Akschota 50mg Oil Urumana 5mg
Phenoxyethanol

Akschota (Juglans Regia): Natural and effective exfoliant used in face scrub to remove dead skin cells, unclog pores, and promote a smoother, more radiant complexion.

Oil Urumana (Prunus Armeniaca): Used in removing embedded dirt particles on the skin as well as dead skin cells to result in clean and glowing skin.

Phenoxyethenol: Acts as a broad-spectrum preservative, preventing microbial growth and ensuring product stability and safety.

Manufacturer: Zydus Wellness Product Ltd, Near Mamring Power House, Mamring, Namchin-737 132, Sikkim, India.

Batch no: WEA0719 Mfg Date: 07/24 MRP: Rs 15.00

Observation Table:

Table no. 7.1: Evaluation Parameter

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation Of Formulated Product	Observation Of Marketed Product
1.	Colour	Yellowish Brown	Sunlight yellow
2.	Odour	Characteristics	Characteristics
3.	Consistency	Good	Good
4.	Homogeneity and Texture	Smooth	Smooth
5.	Spreadability	Easily Spread	Easily Spread
6.	Washability	Easily washable	Easily washable
7.	Skin irritation	Non-irritant	Non-irritant
8.	pH	7.2	7.3

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS:

Appearance

The prepared scrub was evaluated for its odour and colour. The colour was found to be Yellowish brown in colour and odour was found to be characteristics.

Consistency

It was found to be Granules and homogeneity was smooth with visual observation.

Spreadability

The Spreadability is very important in the behavior of scrub. It is used to identify the extend of Spreadability by the scrub on the skin. A small quantity of sample was placed on a glass slide and

another slide was placed above them; 100 g of weight was placed on the slide. The time taken for the Scrub to spread on the slide was noted and measured which was found to be 4 cm in 60 sec. It was found to be easily spreadable.

Irritability

A small amount of the Scrub was applied on the skin and kept for few minutes and found to be non-irritated.

Washability

A little quantity of Scrub was applied over the skin and was wash with water and it was easily washable.

pH

pH of formulation was measured by using a digital pH meter and result was found to be 7.3.

CONCLUSION

The aim of formulating an Herbal face scrub was found to successful with good result. It was a successful attempt to formulate the anti-bacterial herbal face. The above effects its miles concluded that new formulation of panchamrut herbal scrub can be steady to use and the sugar as a scrubbing/cleansing agent showing correct effects and as frequently additives are natural additives so opportunities for side effects are less. It can be used for any type of pores and skin i.e. Normal pores, oily pores and dry pores. It gives pleasant effects and makes the skin glowing and healthy. The Everyuth Walnut Scrub is generally well regarded for expoliating properties. It effectively removes dead skin cells, promoting smoother and clearer skin. It's important to follow up with moisturizing after use to prevent dryness.

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